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Auxiliary Joining element with integrated Pin structures

Mechanical joining of fiber-reinforced plastic with metal

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Motivation and objective

Initial situation

- High lightweight potential of fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP)
- Increasing use of FRP in industry
 - Multi material design with FRP and metal

State of the art

- FRP-components not suitable for punctual load → Lack of plasticity of the FRP, stress concentrations → Failure of the laminate/joint
 - Current FRP-metal joints only designed for low load capacity

Objective

- Development of an **Auxiliary Joining element with integrated Pin structure (AJP)** to increase the load-bearing capacity of mechanically joined FRP-metal joints
- Design of the pin structure for the optimization of the load condition in the FRP component

Mechanism of action of the structured Auxiliary Joining element

Experimental: quasistatic shear test

- Extensive load transferring into the FRP with AJP possible
- Increasing load-bearing capacity of the screwed FRP-metal combinations with AJP compared with the screwed joints with conventional washer

Fracture characteristics of the FRP

Auxiliary Joining element with Pin structure

Conventional washer

Test method	Quasistatic shear test
Test velocity	$v = 10 \text{ mm/min}$
Test machine	Zwick Z100
Steel material	HC340LA ($t = 1.5 \text{ mm}$)
FRP material	GF-PA6 ($t = 2.0 \text{ mm}$)
Joining technology / joining element	Screw: M5 x 20 (torque: 2 Nm)
Structured auxiliary joining element	1.4301 ($t = 1.5 \text{ mm}$; Pin-length $l = 1.3 \text{ mm}$)
Application method / number of specimen n	Ultrasonic ($n = 5$)
Specimen geometry	According to DVS/EFB 3480-1 Steel: $105 \times 45 \text{ mm}^2$ (edge distance: 8 mm) FRP: $110 \times 45 \text{ mm}^2$ (edge distance: 16 mm)

Summary

Aim

- Development of an Auxiliary Joining element with integrated Pin structure to increase the load-bearing capacity of mechanically joined FRP-metal joints
- Design of the pin structure for the optimization of the load condition in the FRP component

Results

- Development of different insertion methods: ultrasonic-assisted insertion shows the highest usage potential
 - Low-damage insertion with realistic station times possible
 - Implementation of a manufacturing concept for Auxiliary Joining elements suitable for series production
 - Design of a setting tool concept for blind riveting with AJP
 - Corrosion protection of the Auxiliary Joining element by using titanium elements
- **Increase of the load bearing capacity more than 40%**

Thank you very much for your attention!

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